

Rutin from the Flowers of *Cleome gynandra* Linn.

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Cleome gynandra Linn. Syn. *C. pentaphylla* Linn., *Gynandropsis gynandra* (L.) Briq., *G. pentaphylla* D.C. belonging to the Capparaceae, is an erect rather showy glandular pubescent herb with white flowers^{1,2}. The leaves are eaten as a pot-herb and used for flavouring purposes in sauces³. The leaves and the seeds of the plant are used in indigenous medicine in the same way as mustard⁴. A decoction of the roots possesses mild febrifugal property. β -Sitosterol- β -D-glucoside and kaempferol have been isolated from the seeds of the plant⁵. Glucoiberine, glucocapparine and neoglucobrassicin and glucobrassicin have also been isolated from the plant⁶. Autolysis product of *C. gynandra* was analysed by high sensitivity GC/MS and was identified as methylglucosinolate⁷.

Here, we report the isolation of rutin from the flowers of *C. gynandra*. Rutin is reported to be fairly common in Capparaceae⁸ and its isolation is in conformity with its taxonomic status.

Fresh white flower petals of *C. gynandra* were extracted and fractionated in the usual way⁹. The residue obtained from EtOAc fraction was recrystallised from Me₂CO and subjected to PC, hydrolytic studies, uv, ¹H and ¹³C nmr and MS studies. The yellow solid (0.75 g/1 kg of petals) showed m.p. 188°; λ_{max} (MeOH) 257, 281, 297sh, 360; +NaOMe 273, 325, 411; +AlCl₃ 273, 305sh, 435; +(AlCl₃-HCl) 269, 301, 364, 399; + NaOAc 273, 301sh, 313, 377; +NaOAc-H₃BO₃ 265, 301, 372 nm; ¹H nmr δ (90 MHz, DMSO-d₆; TMS) 7.3 (2H, d, J 2 Hz, H-2' and H-6'), 6.7 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-5'), 6.0 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-6), 6.2 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz, H-8), 5.2 (gluc H-1''), 4.4 (rhamn H-1'''), 0.8-1.1 (rhamn-Me); ¹³C nmr (67.89 MHz; DMSO-d₆; TMS) 157.10 (C-2), 133.10 (C-3), 177.23 (C-4), 160.80 (C-5), 98.71 (C-6), 163.74 (C-7), 93.72 (C-8), 156.91 (C-9), 103.90 (C-10), 121.70 (C-1'), 115.12 (C-2'), 144.33 (C-3'), 148.00 (C-4'), 116.20 (C-5'), 121.10 (C-6'), 101.30 (C-1''), 73.82 (C-2''), 76.00 (C-3''), 70.34 (C-4''), 75.30

(C-5''), 66.80 (C-6''), 100.40 (C-1'''), 70.10 (C-2'''), 69.71 (C-3'''), 71.70 (C-4'''), 68.00 (C-5'''), 17.10 (C-6'''); m/z (rel. int. %) 302 (100%) (aglycone M⁺), 153 (58%) (RDA fragment of A-ring with proton shift), 137 (64%), 109 (60%), 284 (20%), 274 (20%), 152 (18%), 134 (18%).

From these results, the co-tlc data and m.m.p. with an authentic sample of rutin obtained from *Wrightia tinctoria*¹⁰, the identity of the compound was established as rutin.

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